

Structural, Optical and Morphological Studies of WO₃ Thin Films Prepared by Pulse Electrodeposition (50:50) Method

A. J. More^{1*}

¹ Department of Physics, Vidya Vikas Mandal's Art's, Science and Commerce College Sakri, Tal. Sakri, Dist. Dhule, MS, India

Abstract

Tungsten oxide (WO₃) thin films were successfully deposited on indium tin oxide (ITO) coated glass substrates using a pulse electrodeposition method. Peroxotungstic acid (PTA) precursor solution was synthesized by the controlled reaction of tungsten metal powder with hydrogen peroxide. The prepared films were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), UV-Visible spectroscopy, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to investigate their structural, optical, and surface morphological properties. XRD study shows that the as deposited WO₃ samples are amorphous. Confirmation of material is from the micro-Raman study. Optical studies revealed high transparency in the visible region with a well-defined absorbance edge. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) micrographs showed uniform and compact surface morphology. These results demonstrate that the pulse deposition technique is an effective and low-cost method for the fabrication of high-quality WO₃ thin films suitable for optoelectronic and electrochromic applications.

Keywords: WO₃ thin films, Pulse deposition, Peroxotungstic acid, Optical properties, SEM, XRD

*Corresponding author: dranupmore@gmail.com

Received: 12 January 2026

Revised: 4 February 2026

Accepted: 13 February 2026

Copyright ♥ authors 2026

898

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26643/rb.v11i18i10.9320>

Introduction

Transition metal oxide (TMO) thin films have attracted considerable attention due to their wide range of applications in electrochromic devices, gas sensors, smart windows, photocatalysis, and energy storage systems. Among them, tungsten oxide (WO_3) is a well-known n-type semiconductor exhibiting excellent electrochromic behavior, high chemical stability, and good optical transparency in the visible region [1].

Various techniques such as sol–gel, sputtering, chemical vapor deposition, spray pyrolysis, and electrodeposition have been employed for the preparation of WO_3 thin films. However, many of these methods require high vacuum systems, elevated temperatures, or complex instrumentation. Solution-based deposition techniques offer advantages such as low cost, large-area coating capability, and ease of composition control [2].

Pulse deposition is an emerging technique that allows controlled growth of thin films by alternating deposition and relaxation cycles. In this work, WO_3 thin films were prepared using a pulse deposition method with peroxotungstic acid (PTA) as the precursor. The structural, optical, and morphological properties of the pulse electrodeposited films were systematically investigated.

Experimental Details

PTA precursor solution was synthesized by reacting tungsten metal powder with hydrogen peroxide, 9.192 g of tungsten metal powder (99% purity, Sigma-Aldrich) was gradually added to 100 ml of 30% hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) at room temperature. The reaction is highly exothermic; therefore, tungsten powder was added slowly under continuous stirring, and the reaction vessel was maintained in an ice-cold bath to control the temperature. The solution was stirred continuously for 48 hours, during which complete dissolution of tungsten occurred, forming a clear and colorless PTA solution. The resulting PTA can be represented as $\text{WO}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \cdot m\text{H}_2\text{O}$, depending on synthesis conditions [3]. To prepare the deposition solution, 50 ml of PTA was mixed with 60% ethanol and 40% double-distilled water. The solution was refluxed at 60 °C for 25 minutes to remove excess water and hydrogen peroxide. After refluxing, a yellow-colored acid solution was obtained, indicating the formation of a suitable precursor for WO_3 thin-film deposition.

Deposition of WO₃ Thin Films

WO₃ thin films were deposited on ITO-coated glass substrates using the pulse deposition (50:50) method. In this technique, equal on-time and off-time pulses were applied to ensure uniform film growth and controlled nucleation. The substrates were thoroughly cleaned prior to deposition to ensure good adhesion and film uniformity.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows the XRD pattern of the WO₃ thin film deposited using the pulse deposition (50:50) method. The XRD spectrum exhibit a broad hump in the low 2θ region due to the glass and the major peaks are of ITO (JCPDS card # 00-039-1058), all peaks have been assigned to the characteristics of ITO, confirming that WO₃ thin films are of amorphous nature.

Figure 1 XRD pattern of the WO₃ thin film

micro-Raman Spectroscopy

Figure 2 shows the micro-Raman spectrum of the WO₃ thin film. The chemical structure and functional groups of galvanostatically electrodeposited WO₃ thin films were studied with the help of micro-Raman spectroscopy. The peaks provide the information about a-WO₃ thin films. Figure 2 shows the micro-Raman spectrum of the WO₃ thin film. An intense peak centered at ~950 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{W}=\text{O})$ structure of WO₃ [4-5]. For the electrodeposition, ITO substrate is used, so the other peaks generated are due to ITO. The peaks at 302, 452, 560, 779 and 1092 cm⁻¹ are attributed to ITO substrate. The peak 302 cm⁻¹ is attributed to In-O-In [6], 452 cm⁻¹ is attributed to

δ (Si–O_b–Si) [7], 560 cm⁻¹ is attributed to δ (Si–O_b–Si) [7], 779 cm⁻¹ is attributed to Si–O stretching [8] and 1092 cm⁻¹ is attributed to antisymmetric stretching of C–O [9]. Two additional peaks are seen at 240 cm⁻¹ [10-11] and 376 cm⁻¹ [12] assigned to WO₃.H₂O ν (W–OH₂) stretching mode which confirming WO₃ with hydrated content. The peak at 950 cm⁻¹ which is found in WO₃ samples, is of particular relevance and deserves special consideration. A feature around 950 cm⁻¹, due to W=O stretching vibration, is associated to film nanostructuring [13]: the involved bonds are mainly located at surface sites, thus a comparatively high intensity. From micro-Raman analysis, it is confirmed that the deposited thin film is of tungsten oxide with hydrated content is present.

Figure 2 micro-Raman spectrum of the WO₃ thin film

Optical Properties

Figure 3 presents the UV–Visible absorbance spectrum of the WO₃ thin film with respect to the ITO substrate. The film shows strong absorbance in the UV region and low absorbance in the visible region, indicating good transparency.

Figure 3 UV-Visible absorbance spectrum of the WO_3 thin film

Figure 4 shows the transmittance spectrum, revealing high optical transmittance in the visible range, which is a desirable property for smart window and display applications. The sharp absorption edge suggests good optical quality and uniform film thickness.

Figure 4 Transmittance spectrum of the WO_3 thin film

The optical behavior of the films can be attributed to the electronic transitions between the valence band and conduction band of WO_3 , as well as the nanocrystalline structure obtained through pulse deposition.

Surface Morphology (SEM)

SEM micrographs of the WO_3 thin film are shown in Figure 5. The images reveal a uniform, dense, and crack-free surface morphology. The grains are well distributed over the substrate, indicating homogeneous nucleation and growth during pulse deposition. Such compact morphology enhances the optical transparency and improves the electrochemical stability of the films, making them suitable for device applications.

Figure 5 SEM micrographs of the WO_3 thin film

Conclusion

WO_3 thin films were successfully fabricated on ITO substrates using a pulse electrodeposition (50:50) method with peroxotungstic acid precursor. XRD study shows that the as deposited WO_3 sample is amorphous. Formation of WO_3 with presence of hydrated content is evident from the micro-Raman study. Optical studies showed high transparency in the visible region, while SEM analysis revealed uniform and compact surface morphology. The results demonstrate that pulse deposition is a simple, cost-effective, and efficient technique for preparing high-quality WO_3 thin films for optoelectronic, electrochromic, and sensing applications.

References

1. C. G. Granqvist, "Handbook of inorganic electrochromic materials", Elsevier, Netherlands, 2002.
2. S. R. Bathe and P. S. Patil, "Electrochromic characteristics of fibrous reticulated WO₃ thin films prepared by pulsed spray pyrolysis technique," *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 91, p. 1097, 2007
3. E. A. Meulenkaamp, "Mechanism of WO₃ electrodeposition from peroxy-tungstate solution," *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, vol. 144, p. 1664, 1997
4. S. H. Lee, H. M. Cheong, C. E. Tracy, A. Mascarenhas, D. K. Benson, and S. K. Deb, "Raman spectroscopic studies of electrochromic a-WO₃," *Electrochim. Acta*, vol. 44, p. 3111, 1999.
5. M. Breedon, P. Spizzirri, M. Taylor, J. Du Plessis, D. McCulloch, J. Zhu, L. Yu, Z. Hu, C. Rix, W. Wlodarski, and K. Kalantar-zadeh, "Synthesis of nanostructured tungsten oxide thin films: A simple, controllable, inexpensive, aqueous sol-gel method," *Cryst. Growth Des.*, vol. 10, p. 430, 2010
6. M. Rojas-López, J. Nieto-Navarro, E. Rosendo, H. Navarro-Contreras, and M. A. Vidal, "Raman scattering study of photoluminescent spark-processed porous InP," *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 379, p. 1, 2000
7. P. Makreski, G. Jovanovski, B. Kaitner, A. Gajović, and T. Biljan, "Minerals from macedonia XVIII. Vibrational spectra of some sorosilicates," *Vib. Spectrosc.*, vol. 44, p. 162, 2007
8. G. Jovanovski, P. Makreski, B. Kaitner, and B. Boev, "Silicate minerals from macedonia. Complementary use of vibrational spectroscopy and X-ray powder diffraction for identification and detection purposes," *Croat. Chem. acta*, vol. 82, p. 363, 2009
9. R. S. Luo and J. Jonas, "Raman scattering study of liquid ethylene glycol confined to nanoporous silica glasses," *J. Raman Spectrosc.*, vol. 32, p. 975, 2001
10. M. F. Daniel, B. Desbat, J. C. Lassegues, B. Gerand, and M. Figlarz, "Infrared and Raman study of WO₃ tungsten trioxides and W_{0.3}xH₂O tungsten trioxide hydrates," *J. Solid State Chem.*, vol. 67, p. 235, 1987.

11. M. Epifani, T. Andreu, J. Arbiol, R. Díaz, P. Siciliano, and J. R. Morante, “Chloro-alkoxide route to transition metal oxides. Synthesis of WO₃ thin films and powders from a tungsten chloro-methoxide,” *Chem. Mater.*, vol. 21, p. 5215, 2009
12. J. Z. Ou, M. H. Yaacob, M. Breedon, H. D. Zheng, J. L. Campbell, K. Latham, J. du Plessis, W. Wlodarski, and K. Kalantar-Zadeh, “In situ Raman spectroscopy of H₂ interaction with WO₃ films,” *Phys. chem. chem. phys*, vol. 13, p. 7330, 2011
13. N. Santo, M. Filipescu, P. M. Ossi, and M. Dinescu, “Nanostructure evolution in cluster-assembled WO_x films synthesized by radio-frequency assisted laser ablation,” *Appl. Phys. A Mater. Sci. Process.*, vol. 101, p. 325, 2010